

Skin cancer prevention: which strategy is the most promising?

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Abstract

Malignant neoplasms of the skin are among the most common types of cancer worldwide. These include malignant melanoma and neoplasms of epithelial origin such as basal cell carcinoma (BCC) and squamous cell carcinoma (SCC). In recent decades, the incidence of these diseases has been steadily rising, making skin cancer increasingly important at the population level. The main reason for this increase in the incidence rate is the increasing exposure of the skin to UV radiation caused by changes in leisure time behavior, the use of solariums and the thinning of the ozone layer. This development must be counteracted by primary and secondary prevention strategies in order to reduce morbidity and mortality (especially for malignant melanoma) in the long term.

Introduction

The incidence of malignant melanoma is currently increasing faster than that of all other tumors. It is already the tenth most common fatal cancer. Of people born in the 1920s, one in about 1,500 developed malignant melanoma at some point in their lives. Of people born in 1999, projections indicate that one in 100 will be diagnosed with this disease. The incidence of the disease would thus increase more than 20-fold. The incidence of malignant melanoma in Europe is currently up to 15 new cases per year and 100,000 inhabitants. The incidence of the disease is also increasing in younger age groups, resulting in a higher mortality rate.¹⁻³

By far the largest percentage (>90%) of malignant neoplasms of the skin is represented by non-melanocytic skin cancer, basal cell carcinoma (BCC) and squamous cell carcinoma (SCC). BCC is the most common tumor of the skin. It grows locally invasive and destructive, but almost never metastasizes. The prevalence varies, according to the intensity of sun exposure, from 20-50 per 100,000 population in Northern and Central Europe to 250 per 100,000 population in Australia.³

The prevalence of SCC is about 10 per 100,000 population in central Europe; in sunny countries, it increases to 30 (southern U.S.) and 50 (Australia) per 100,000 population. The prognosis of SCC of the skin is 80% recurrence-free at 5 years. However, recent figures suggest that the incidences for both malignant melanoma and BCC and SCC may be much higher than the statistics indicate. The reporting system is far from being internationally uniform and entirely reliable.^{10,11,18}

The tasks of primary and secondary prevention are of particular importance. Information and education of the population about health risks of natural and artificial UV radiation is of paramount importance, especially for the reduction of incidences of BCC and SCC. For malignant melanoma, on the other hand, the question of the contribution of UV radiation to its development is not quite so clear, and research has not yet done its homework sufficiently in this area.^{3,10,11}

The General Public

Improving the knowledge of the general public, the medical profession and political decision-makers about the importance of early detection of skin cancer is therefore just as important as learning how to recognize suspicious skin lesions yourself. Humans as such are endowed with a fine sense of pattern recognition. The recognition of patterns in the appearance and behavior of a skin area that are typically considered to be suspicious can be taught to an averagely intelligent person and should therefore be urgently included in education and training for providers of body-related services. For example, an appropriately trained physiotherapist may well be able to recognize suspicious lesions as reliably as a general practitioner.^{6,12}

Primary care providers

A spontaneous reflex of many health system officials is to place the burden on primary care physicians to take care of timely detection of skin cancer. The rationale behind this is the idea that the average citizen most frequently sees a family doctor anyway, and then he or she should also take care of their patients' skin health.

But this is naive. Family doctors' practices around the world are working to breaking point, and it would be downright ludicrous to believe that they have the time and expertise to quickly assess the status of the entire skin of a patient.¹⁶

The results of this can be seen in the findings with which patients in family practice-focused health care systems eventually see a dermatologist. It's a disaster. When you compare photographs of the skin tumors that British NHS patients present to dermatologists with those from the U.S., you wonder what the British NHS is actually thinking by letting its citizens walk on such thin ice.^{Not published data from within the Lazar Clinic Group}

In the U.S.A., it is extremely rare for insured patients not to be referred to a dermatologist immediately when there is even only the shadow of a doubt. In the UK, on the other hand, dermatologists see the most bizarre growths that make even seasoned pathologist sweat, simply because NHS GPs have an astonishing and medically difficult to comprehend high tolerance level before sending a patient to a specialist. So GPs with their high volume of patients are neither the best nor the most appropriate address for good protection against advanced skin cancer.^{3,11,16}

Dermatologists

Thorough dermatologic examinations are, of course, the gold standard of skin cancer detection, provided the examination is performed as a dermoscopy, preferably with a digital dermatoscope. Unfortunately, however, it is precisely this elementary device that is still being skimped on in many practices and clinics. In addition, the quality of the diagnosis is closely linked to the quality of the training and experience of the respective dermatologist.

Comprehensive and regular preventive examinations by a dermatologist naturally have a much greater sensitivity than any other procedure, but in the case of SCC and especially malignant melanoma, one must never forget how quickly these can develop. The wrong idea that the dermatologist's full-body screening is a carte blanche for the following months must be countered. This raises the question of whether annual checks by dermatologists do not lull patients into a false sense of security.^{3,8,19}

Well-learned self-observation and a trained eye of physicians of other specialties as well as providers of body-related services is much closer to reality from the point of view of the development dynamics of a SCC or malignant melanoma than "preventive examinations" by

a dermatologist. This is because this type of precautionary examination (screening) is only helpful for a period of around six, or at best up to twelve weeks. However, even in the G7 countries, such close-meshed intervals are only offered to people who have already developed skin cancer; the usual intervals for healthy people are usually 12 to 24 months, which is both too long and useless.^{3,10,11,17}

For dermatologists, "preventive screenings" are a convenient source of additional revenue. Epidemiologically, however, they make no sense at all when performed on healthy patients. If it were really the serious intention of dermatologists to save their patients from SCCs or melanomas in a rather advanced stage, they would have to make appointments four times a year or offer the possibility of digital visual diagnoses at any time. But this is not the case in practically any classic practice or clinic.

Tele-medicine services

A new development are online services where you can send in a photo, whereupon a photographed skin lesion is then analyzed by artificial intelligence (A.I.), by a team of doctors, or a combination of both. In terms of speed and convenience, these services are unbeatable. Services based purely on A.I. are not sufficiently reliable from a scientific point of view, as there are simply not yet enough sufficiently professional studies available. Coupling A.I. with a physician who takes a second look is therefore currently considered the gold standard in this area. However, so far there is no service that regularly offers tele-dermatology. In part, the doctors of some providers work with a series of contrast filters that increase their accuracy. Nevertheless, the maximum of these services corresponds at best to a thorough eye diagnosis, which however should not be underestimated.²⁰⁻²²

Nevertheless, the usefulness of these services depends on the population at large knowing what to look for in terms of a lesion. That is, when it is appropriate to seek help from such a service. Thorough education and training of all people can be achieved through the biology classes in schools. Unfortunately, this is hardly the case in any country.

Cautious monitoring or prompt excision biopsy?

For inexplicable reasons, the majority of dermatologists still tend to adopt a watch-and-wait approach to new nevi or those that have changed minimally. This is despite the fact that excision of a nevus with subsequent evaluation by a pathologist is a small matter, whereas a skin cancer diagnosed too late can shake the patient's life and, in the worst case, bring it to an end. The recommendation for an excision should therefore be made at a very early stage. Many people injure themselves at home or at work more seriously than the wound left by a removed nevus. Of course, this does not apply to patients with wound healing disorders, etc., but these represent only a minority. In general, the dermatologist should bring the scalpel into action already at the words "newly appeared" and "changed".²³

Conclusion

On the basis of what we have discussed, it is clear that the best early detection of skin cancer is done by the patients themselves. They then need the possibility to get an appointment with a dermatologist as soon as possible, who in turn should aim for a surgical solution as early as possible. We are skeptical about screening programs, as they do not do match with the natural course of the disease in skin cancer. Rather, everyone should be given enough knowledge to recognize suspicious lesions in themselves and others.

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Ethical standards, data safety compliance and patient's rights

This article is about scientific facts. It is not reporting on a clinical trial (or anything similar) in its legal definition, especially not a prospective one. Our work was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

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